

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF THE DIFFUSIVE GRADIENT IN THIN FILM TECHNIQUE FOR DETERMINATION OF ARSENIC IN AQUATIC ENVIRONMENT

V. Smolikova^{1,2}, P. Pelcova¹, L. Zlamalova¹, A. Ridoskova^{1,2}

¹*Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Mendel University in Brno. Zemedelska 1, 613 00, Brno,
Czech Republic.*

²*Central European Institute of Technology, Brno University of Technology, Purkynova 656/123, 616 00,
Brno, Czech Republic.*

vendulasmolikova@seznam.cz

A diffusive gradient in thin film technique (DGT) was innovated for more effective determination of the bioavailability of arsenic in aquatic environment. A new and commercially available ion-exchange resin (Lewatit FO 36) containing ferric oxyhydroxide functional groups was used for the manufacture of sorption gels. This polystyrene-based resin is designed to reduce the arsenic contamination in potable water supplies and is able to adsorb arsenate (As^V) as well as arsenite (As^{III}) compounds [1]. The microwave-assisted elution of arsenic from sorption gel was optimized. The mixture of sodium hydroxide (10 g L⁻¹) and sodium chloride (10 g L⁻¹) was used as elution agent. The arsenic contents were determined by electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometer Agilent 280Z Series AA (Agilent Technologies, USA) equipped with Zeeman correction. The mixture of 1% Pd/Mg(NO₃)₂ was used as modifier for arsenic determination.

The diffusion coefficients of arsenic species and capacity of sorption gels were established. Also, various factors (e.g., the pH, chlorides, humic acids, presence of Fe) that may affect the accumulation of this analyte in real environment were investigated. The time-dependence experiments were carried out to test the validity of DGT measurement. The new sorption gel containing ion-exchange resin (Lewatit FO 36) is characterized by homogeneous gel structure, high sorption capability and low time-consuming production.

Topics: Passive sampling and sampling in general, Metals & speciation analysis, Marine & freshwater environment

Acknowledgement: This research was carried out with the support of the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic under the project CEITEC 2020 (LQ1601).

References:

[1] LANXESS Group. Product information – Lewatit® FO 36, 2008.